

Constraints of the First Generation College Girls Students: A Survey

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ABSTRACT

The important factor in one's life is education, because it only moulds one person to have better and bright future. Unfortunately this was denied for girls during the first century. In this article the researcher has tried to find out the level of constraints of first generation College Girls Students and to identify the difference between the constraints of first generation first generation College Girls Students based on the select sub samples -Locality of the learners (Urban/Rural), Course of the study (UG/PG), Stream of the study (Arts/Science). For this purpose the researcher has used a sample of 500 first generation college girls students for collecting data. A self structured questionnaire based on different factors of constraints has been used. Collected data have been analyzed with descriptive statistics and t test. The findings of the study indicate that the level of constraints of first generation College Girls Students is high and there is significant difference of Constraints between the first generation college girl students of different sub samples.

KEYWORDS: cultural growth

INTRODUCTION

Arnold saying in Tamil, tells that "Education is not important for women who are only going to cook for their family". From ancient time onwards women were not given their due respect in the world, in their society, in their village and in their family. However, to understand about family constraints, one should know it's meaning. Above all it is restriction or limit that created by our own blood relationship, it may be a father, mother, brother or grandparents. Many of rural area, parents show interest to send their girl child for higher studies. The lack of awareness that leads to very less encouragement, because of no people were there to guide them and support them because they themselves were not educated and their own brother's and sister's themselves don't help them (Radwin et al., 2013).

Gender inequality, especially in rural areas places a vital role to degrade the progress of women education. In the first century time women were engaged to agricultural work and household work. So they were not aware of higher education. Child-care duties are performed by women and young girls. Another reason was the poor economic status of the

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family. Earning of the family was only sufficient to hand and mouth. As the family burden was being barred to women, they were sent for some work or carried the household works (Mitchell 1997; Terenzini et al., 1996).

The family does not take too much of advantage in dealing with girl child. Many of them take it for granted that they should do all household work, more than slaves. There is no freedom for females to do that they are intended. Since our society is more of tradition, still there is male domination attitude, starts from the family to society. The female are being treated as unpaid servants in all families and societies. This attitude must be eradicated from our society. Otherwise it is a threat to our future society. The family must offer an apt situation and atmosphere to females. They are abused like objects. Not given proper situation and time to do all. Situations are not provided to make decision doing things for the family the way they wanted. Family should be the home of freedom, encouragement, to guide and finally support them in all aspects.

Review of Literature:

In her study "Women Entrepreneurship in India: Challenges and Strategies," (*Mustiary, Begum, 2006*) observed that women's increased participation in the workforce was affected by factors such as shifting cultural norms, higher levels of education and industrialization, and more opportunities for social and professional advancement. While women have made great strides in the previous half-century, they still face a number of obstacles and societal ills in today's male-dominated culture.

In her work "Access of Women to Higher Education," (*Bhadauria, Mridula, 2005*), examines the need of reconsidering women's participation in higher education. Only 38.84% of women now enrol in college, which does not guarantee that they will get a decent education. Without sacrificing quality, universities in smaller cities and towns should expand women's access to technical areas including engineering, medicine, veterinary science, and law. Short-term diversification that can serve the huge unorganized and organized sector should be made more accessible to women. Every university and institution needs to be required to have a women's dorm. More centres and courses for distance learning in higher education should be made available at institutions that primarily serve women. In addition to the aforementioned measures, it is essential to focus on empowering women via education, legislation, and social protections.

NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

The advancement of a nation is greatly aided by its higher education system. Having more women in higher education is crucial to a country's long-term human capital and economic, social, and cultural growth. It paves the way for individuals to have a more fulfilling "life of the mind," which has far-reaching positive effects on society as a whole. In order to have a meritocratic and open society, higher education is necessary. Having a better grasp of society standards, empowering people to think for themselves, and discouraging bias of any kind are all benefits of education. For women to achieve economic independence, social progress, and personal well-being, education is essential. Women continue to face discrimination and abuse in many spheres, including the economy, education, society, politics, health care, nutrition, human rights, and more. To combat the socially built gender prejudices, oppressed women must be given the tools to succeed in all areas of life. Furthermore, they are behind in areas like as

education, communication, health, and family support. And their lack of progress due to this retrograde attitude is a major problem. Women who are able to conceive and raise such offspring may be the ones who steer their nation towards development and wealth. Women's education contributes to a more cultured family and community. Economic growth revolves on innovative business formation. Despite recent progress, entrepreneurship is still stereotyped as an area where men thrive. Women company owners face a number of challenges in addition to the prevalent stereotype (*Meenakshi and Mahapatra, 2015*).

Objectives:

- To find out the level of constraints of first generation College Girls Students
- To identify the difference between the constraints of first generation first generation College Girls Students based on the select sub samples - Locality of the learners (Urban/Rural), Course of the study (UG/PG), Stream of the study (Arts/Science).

Hypothesis:

1. The level of constraints of first generation College Girls Students is high.
2. There is no significant difference between the constraints of first generation College Girls Students based on the select sub samples.

Methodology: The populations included in the present study are the first generation women learners studying in UG and PG programmes in the academic year 2021-22 in Paschim Medinipur and Purba Medinipur districts of West Bengal. In order to carry out the present study the researcher has randomly selected first generation women learners studying in the colleges of Paschim Medinipur and Purba Medinipur districts of West Bengal. The samples of the study included 500 learners from the selected colleges.

The researcher has constructed the questionnaire on constraints of first generation women learners to collect data from the representative of the population. The item framed was based on the factors of Home, Educational, Psychological and Social. The preliminary form of the questionnaire consisted of 54 items for the variable constraints with four points scale (Strongly Agree/Agree/Disagree/Strongly Disagree) and the scoring procedure for the response carries 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively (only positive statements).

Data Analysis:**Table 1-Descriptive Statistics for Constraints of first generation College Girls Students**

Parameters	Values
N	500
Minimum	56
Maximum	177
Mean	119.742
Median	122
SD	25.6931
SEM	1.1490
Skewness	-0.0548
Kurtosis	2.6291

The above table 1 shows the descriptive statistics for the constraints of first generation college girls students. It is clear that the calculated mean score is 119.742 with the minimum range of 56 and maximum range of 177. SD score is 25.6931 and the Standard Error Means is 1.1490 with the Kurtosis value 2.6291. The score range for Needs of first generation college students is 45-180. It is evident that the calculated mean score is higher than the mid value 90. Therefore it can be concluded that the level of constraints of first generation College Girls Students is high. Hence the formulated hypothesis "The level of constraints of first generation College Girls Students is high" is accepted.

Table 2-Difference between the Constraints of first generation first generation College Girls Students based on Locality of Learners

Group	N	Mean	SD	SEM	df	t
Rural	360	122.2438	20.3654	1.073351	498	0.9014
Urban	140	120.3564	22.6327	1.912812		

To find the significant difference between the two sub-groups regarding the Constraints of first generation college girls students on the basis of Locality of Learners the 't' value has been calculated. The table 2 shows that the mean score of constraints for rural girls students is 122.2438 and SD is 20.3654. On the other hand the mean score of the constraints for Urban girls students is 120.3564 and SD is 22.6327. It is found from the above table that the calculated 't' value 0.9014 is found to be not significant. Hence the research null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant difference of constraints between the college girl students of Rural and Urban.

Table 3-Difference between the Constraints of first generation first generation College Girls Students based on Course of the Study

Group	N	Mean	SD	SEM	df	t
UG	310	121.5134	25.2634	1.496475	498	0.3521
PG	190	120.7326	23.5686	1.607365		

To find the significant difference between the two sub-groups regarding the Constraints of first generation college girls students on the basis of Course of the Study the 't' value has been calculated. The table 3 shows that the mean score of constraints for UG girls students is 121.5134 and SD is 25.2634. On the other hand the mean score of the constraints for PG girls students is 120.7326 and SD is 23.5686. It is found from the above table that the calculated 't' value 0.3521 is found to be not significant. Hence the research null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant difference of constraints between the college girl students of UG and PG

Table 4-Difference between the Constraints of first generation first generation College Girls Students based on Stream of the Study

Group	N	Mean	SD	SEM	df	t
Arts	310	121.5684	25.9682	1.474895	498	0.5067
Science	190	120.3425	26.7324	1.939372		

To find the significant difference between the two sub-groups regarding the constraints of first generation college girls students on the basis of Stream of the Study the 't' value has been calculated. The table 4 shows that the mean score of constraints for Arts girls students is 121.5684 and SD is 25.9682. On the other hand the mean score of the constraints for Science girls students is 120.3425 and SD is 26.7324. It is found from the above table that the calculated 't' value 0.5067 is found to be not significant. Hence the research null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant difference of constraints between the college girl students of Arts and Science.

Findings:

- The level of constraints of first generation College Girls Students is high
- There is significant difference of Constraints between the first generation college girl students of different sub samples.

Conclusion:

The obstacles mentioned by the learners are infrastructural facilities in college and transportation is difficult for the rural women learners. Arts and science students do not properly get the scholarship. Students those who studied in Tamil medium in schools find it difficult to understand English and also the class strength is more so teachers do not find time to focus on all the students. Taiyyibah et al. (2016) the findings of the study indicated that the girls face enormously difficult situations in the process of getting admission into higher educational institutions.

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